

Online Monitoring for Multi-Object Measurement Model Parameters

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Online Monitoring for Multi-Object Measurement Model Parameters

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Abstract—Model-based multi-sensor multi-object tracking approaches crucially depend on their prediction and measurement models. Typically, the approaches work well if the models and their parameters fit the current situation. For a safe operation, it is, therefore, crucial to continuously monitor them. In general, no performance guarantees for the filter can be made in the case of non-fitting models. On the other hand, if the models match, the mathematical properties of the tracking approach, such as Bayes optimality, apply. Distinguishing the two cases leads to a more interpretable and trustable tracking result and provides useful insights for modules later in the processing chain. This paper proposes two methods for monitoring two different parameters of the multi-object measurement model. The evaluation based on simulated data shows that both methods can detect wrong filter parameters, which enhances the reliability of the tracking approach.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the field of automated driving, the self-assessment of functional components is crucial for ensuring safe operation. This is also significant for legislation where ongoing self-monitoring may be obligatory, as, e.g., in Germany [1]. The environmental model is particularly important, as both planning and decision-making depend on its accuracy.

In this work, we consider model-based multi-sensor multi-object tracking as the approach for creating the environment model. It is based on Bayes theorem with explicit measurement and process models. Typically, this works well if the process and measurement models closely resemble the actual behavior of objects and the sensors or detectors. Then, the usual performance of the used filter can be expected. If, however, the models do not fit, performance can not be guaranteed. For safe usage of the tracking result in later processing units, it is, therefore, crucial to detect such situations and either, e.g., flag the tracking result as unreliable or adjust the tracking parameters if possible. On the other hand, it is also beneficial to detect situations where good performance can be expected. Note that traditional tracking metrics are not appropriate for this task because they rely on ground-truth information, which is, of course, not available online during operation.

Traditionally, tracking algorithms are formulated with prediction and update steps. During the prediction, a process model that describes the movement of objects is used to

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propagate the last result to the next time step. Additionally, the birth of new tracks and the death of existing tracks are modeled. With the finite set statistics framework, the prediction step is given by the multi-target Chapman-Kolmogorov equation

$$\pi(X^+) = \int f(X^+|X)\pi(X)\delta X, \quad (1)$$

where the integral is defined as set integral, f is the process model that describes the evolution of the multi-object state, and π denotes probability density functions (pdf) over a random finite set (RFS) X respective X^+ , c.f. [2] for details.

Then, conditioned on the current measurements, the predicted density is updated using the measurement model. Formally, this is given by

$$\pi(X|Z) = \frac{g(Z|X^+)\pi(X^+)}{\pi(Z)} = \frac{g(Z|X^+)\pi(X^+)}{\int g(Z|X^+)\pi(X^+)\delta X^+}, \quad (2)$$

where g is the measurement model. The standard measurement model describes the spatial distribution of the measurements as well as clutter and missed detections [2].

In this work, we focus on two parts of the measurement model. The first part models the clutter measurements. These are measurements that do not belong to any object. In the standard measurement model, clutter is modeled as a Poisson process with clutter intensity κ . The second part is the detection probability. It describes the probability an object generates a measurement, i.e., gets detected. In the standard measurement model, this is modeled with a Bernoulli distribution with detection probability p_d , and each object is independent of the others.

In this work, we propose two different methods for monitoring the two previously described parameters of the multi-object measurement model. One method uses previously published estimation methods [3], [4] together with Bayesian testing. The other method is based on Bayesian model comparison with the Bayes factor. Both methods are able to monitor both types of parameters.

It is important to note that both methods do not modify a tracking algorithm itself but work with an existing algorithm. Both methods extend the algorithm with the aim of providing additional information. Therefore, the methods described in this paper can, with reasonable adaptations, be applied to different filters, e.g., to the labeled multi-Bernoulli (LMB) filter [5], the generalized LMB (GLMB) filter [6], and the Poisson multi-Bernoulli mixture (PMBM) filters [7]. In this paper, the experiments and simulations are performed with an LMB filter.

In summary, we

- propose two different methods for monitoring two different parameters of the multi-object measurement model,
- and evaluate the methods with Monte-Carlo (MC) simulations.

II. FOUNDATIONS AND RELATED WORK

In this section, we briefly sum up the basis of this work. This includes an introduction to the GLMB and LMB filters, methods for estimating the clutter rate and detection probability, and Bayesian testing.

A. Generalized Labeled Multi-Bernoulli Filter

The GLMB filter uses the GLMB density to recursively compute Eq. (1) and Eq. (2). The GLMB density is closed under these equations when using the standard process and measurement model [6]. This means a predicted and updated GLMB is again a GLMB distribution. For more details and thorough definitions, see, e.g., [6]. Because we focus on the parameters of the measurement model, understanding the update equation is sufficient. We formulate the equations in δ -GLMB form, which is slightly more efficient to implement.

If the prior is a δ -GLMB distribution given by

$$\pi(X) = \Delta(X) \sum_{(I,\xi) \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{L}) \times \Xi} w^{I,\xi} \delta_I(\mathcal{L}(X)) [p^\xi]^X, \quad (3)$$

then, with the standard measurement model, the posterior is also a δ -GLMB distribution of the form [6]

$$\pi(X|Z) = \Delta(X) \sum_{\substack{(I,\xi) \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{L}) \times \Xi \\ \theta \in \Theta}} w^{I,\xi,\theta} \delta_I(\mathcal{L}(X)) [p^{\xi,\theta}(\cdot|Z)]^X, \quad (4)$$

with

$$w^{I,\xi,\theta}(Z) \propto w^{I,\xi} \left[\eta_Z^{\xi,\theta} \right]^I, \quad (5a)$$

$$p^{\xi,\theta}(x, l|Z) = \frac{p^\xi(x, l) \psi_Z(x, l, \theta)}{\eta_Z^{\xi,\theta}(l)} \quad (5b)$$

$$\eta_Z^{\xi,\theta}(l) = \langle p^\xi(\cdot, l), \psi_Z(\cdot, l, \theta) \rangle, \quad (5c)$$

$$\psi_Z(x, l, \theta) = \begin{cases} 1 - p_d(x, l) & \theta(l) = 0 \\ \frac{p_d(x, l) g(z_{\theta(l)}|x, l)}{\kappa(z_{\theta(l)})} & \text{else.} \end{cases} \quad (5d)$$

Here, $X \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{X} \times \mathbb{L})$ is the set of all tracks, where one track is given by its kinematic part $x \in \mathbb{X}$ and its label $l \in \mathbb{L}$. \mathbb{X} and \mathbb{Z} are the state and measurement space, $\mathcal{F}(A)$ is the set of all finite subsets of a set A , $Z \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{Z})$ is the multi-object measurement, Θ is the space of all valid measurement-to-track associations, Ξ keeps track of the previous associations, and δ is the generalized Kronecker delta with $\delta_Y(X) = 1$ if $Y = X$ and $\delta_Y(X) = 0$ otherwise. The operator \mathcal{L} is the projection into the label space, and Δ indicates whether a labeled set is valid, i.e., has unique labels. The notation $[f]^A$, where f is a value that depends on $a \in A$ and A is a set, is defined as $[f]^A := \prod_{a \in A} f(a)$.

It is important to notice that one hypothesis (I, ξ, θ) describes one possible set of tracks together with one possible association from these tracks to the measurements. The weight $w^{I,\xi,\theta}$ can then be interpreted as the probability of that specific situation [6].

B. Labeled Multi-Bernoulli Filter

The LMB filter uses a LMB distribution of the form

$$\pi(X) = \Delta(X) [1 - r]^{\mathbb{L} \setminus \mathcal{L}(X)} [r]^{\mathbb{L} \cap \mathcal{L}(X)} [p]^X \quad (6)$$

for the description of the multi-object state. The LMB distribution is a special case of a GLMB distribution. Unlike the GLMB distribution, the LMB distribution is only closed under the prediction and not under the update [5]. There are mainly two methods to compute the update. Both methods compute the LMB distribution that matches the first statistical moment of the GLMB posterior when using the LMB distribution Eq. (6) as prior for Eq. (4).

The first method transforms the LMB to a GLMB distribution, updates this GLMB, and approximates the result with an LMB, c.f. [5]. This results in a LMB distribution defined by its parameters $\{r^\ell, p^\ell\}_{\ell \in \mathbb{L}}$ with [5]

$$r^\ell = \sum_{\substack{(I,\xi) \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{L}) \times \Xi \\ \theta \in \Theta}} \mathbb{1}_I(l) w^{(I,\xi,\theta)}(Z), \quad (7a)$$

$$p^\ell = \frac{1}{r^\ell} \sum_{\substack{(I,\xi) \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{L}) \times \Xi \\ \theta \in \Theta}} \mathbb{1}_I(l) w^{(I,\xi,\theta)}(Z) p^\theta(x, l|Z), \quad (7b)$$

where $\mathbb{1}_A$ is the indicator function of A , i.e., $\mathbb{1}_A(a) = 1$ for $a \in A$ and 0 otherwise.

The second method uses loopy belief propagation to directly calculate the parameters of the updated LMB without first converting it to a GLMB distribution. Because of this, the second method is generally superior in both complexity and performance compared to the first one [8]. However, it is not given in closed form but rather as a fixpoint iteration.

C. Clutter Rate Estimation

In our paper [3], we show a method to estimate the clutter rate parameter based on information computed by the filter during the update step. It assumes a constant clutter intensity κ . This means the clutter process is completely specified through the clutter rate $\lambda = \langle \kappa, 1 \rangle = \lambda A$, where A is the volume of the measurement space.

The method estimates the distribution of the clutter rate in the form of a Gamma distribution, i.e., an estimation of the clutter rate λ is of the form $\lambda \sim \text{Gamma}(\alpha, \beta)$, where $\text{Gamma}(\alpha, \beta)$ is the Gamma distribution with parameters $\alpha > 0$ and $\beta > 0$ and pdf

$$f(\lambda) = \frac{\beta^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \lambda^{\alpha-1} e^{-\beta\lambda} \quad (8)$$

for $\lambda > 0$ and 0 otherwise. Here, Γ is the Gamma function. For this, a prior Gamma distribution is updated using the distribution of the number of clutter measurements. The computation of the distribution of the number of clutter measurements is based on the filter update. For the GLMB and LMB filters, it is given by a sum of the corresponding weights of the posterior Eq. (4). More details can be found in [3].

The prior must be specified beforehand and should reflect the prior knowledge about a sensor. For example, a LiDAR sensor typically has a lower clutter rate than a radar sensor. In

Fig. 1: Example of the clutter rate estimation. The prior knowledge of the sensor is encoded in the blue Gamma distribution. The estimation after some update steps is shown in yellow. A priori, we expect a mean clutter rate of 7 but are not sure about the actual value, which is expressed by the relatively high variance of 10. The posterior distribution shows that the data support a lower clutter rate with a mean value of 5. Because more information is included in the posterior, the variance is lower compared to the prior.

Fig. 2: Example of the detection probability estimation. The prior knowledge is encoded in the blue Beta distribution, and the estimation after some filter steps is shown in yellow. Additionally, the 95% HDI of the posterior is shown in yellow, and the ROPE of the filter parameter is shown in green.

Fig. 1, you see an example of a prior and updated estimation. One remark is necessary: As the method uses information from the update step and the filter uses a certain clutter rate during that update, the estimation depends on that value. So, when the true clutter rate is strongly different than the filter parameter, this may negatively affect the estimation.

D. Detection Probability Estimation

In [4], we show a similar method to estimate the detection probability. Here, the method uses a Beta distribution, i.e., an estimation of p_d is given by $p_d \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha_0, \alpha_1)$, where $\text{Beta}(\alpha_0, \alpha_1)$ is the Beta distribution with parameters $\alpha_0 > 0$ and $\alpha_1 > 0$ and pdf

$$f(p_d) = \frac{1}{B(\alpha_0, \alpha_1)} p_d^{\alpha_0-1} (1-p_d)^{\alpha_1-1}, \quad (9)$$

for $p_d \in [0, 1]$ and 0 otherwise. $B(\alpha_0, \alpha_1) := \frac{\Gamma(\alpha_0)\Gamma(\alpha_1)}{\Gamma(\alpha_0+\alpha_1)}$ is the Beta function. See Fig. 2 for an example. The method assumes a state-independent detection probability p_d . As before, the prior Beta distribution, used to encode the a priori knowledge about a sensor, is updated using information computed by the filter during the update step. The update depends on the joint distribution of the total number of tracks and the number of detected tracks, i.e., the distribution of detecting k out of t objects. For GLMB and LMB distributions, this joint distribution is given by a sum of the weights of corresponding hypotheses of the posterior Eq. (4). See [4] for more details.

E. Bayesian Testing based on Parameter Estimation

In various fields of science, there is a trend from traditional frequentists to Bayesian statistics. See, e.g., [9] for a discussion of the main reasons.

Since the two previously described estimation methods directly provide the (approximate) posterior distribution of the parameters, we may also consider them Bayesian. Now, if one needs to make the dichotomous decision of whether one parameter is right or wrong, one inevitably loses information compared to the full posterior. A simple method for making such a decision is to use regions of practical equivalence (ROPE) and highest density intervals (HDI).

The idea is to compare the parameter used with the HDI, i.e., the most likely, say 95%, values of the estimation. The problem is that with an increasing number of data, the HDI interval gets smaller, so eventually, ignoring simulations where the exact value of a parameter is known, all parameters fall out of the HDI interval and are therefore considered wrong.

To solve this issue, the parameter is enclosed in an ROPE. The ROPE should include all values that, from a practical perspective, do not affect the results. For example, it should be not relevant whether $p_d = 0.7$ or $p_d = 0.7001$ is chosen for the detection probability. Now, the parameter is only considered wrong if its ROPE does not overlap with the HDI [9]. Typical choices of the HDI are either the 95% or 89% interval [9]. Note that the $(1-\alpha)\%$ HDI of a pdf f is formally defined as the subset I with [10]

$$I(f_\alpha) := \{x: f(x) \geq f_\alpha\} \quad (10)$$

where f_α is the largest constant such that $P(x \in I(f_\alpha)) \geq 1 - \alpha$. Note, that if the ROPE and HDI do not overlap, the probability of a mismatching parameter is greater than $1 - \alpha$.

Figure 2 shows an example with the detection probability. The yellow interval shows the 95% HDI of the posterior, and the green interval shows the ROPE of the filter parameter around $p_d = 0.7$. Because the two intervals overlap, the filter parameter would be considered ok.

F. Bayesian Testing based on Model Comparison

An alternative idea is to define different models and choose the model for which the observed data is more likely. Formally, this is done with the Bayes factor [9].

The Bayes factor can be used to select among competing models M_0 and M_1 with parameters θ_0 and θ_1 after observing some data D . Using Bayes theorem, the posterior odds of the two models are

$$\frac{P(M_0|D)}{P(M_1|D)} = \frac{P(D|M_0) P(M_0)}{P(D|M_1) P(M_1)}. \quad (11a)$$

Here, the likelihood ratio $B_{01} = P(D|M_0)/P(D|M_1) \in \mathbb{R}_+$ is called Bayes factor. It expresses how much a rational agent changes his prior in the light of observed data [9].

There are several scales for interpreting this factor. We use the interpretation given in Table I. Note that only $B_{01} > 1$, i.e., values that enhance the support in model 0, are shown

TABLE I: Interpreting the Bayes factor according to Jeffreys [11].

B_{01}	STRENGTH OF EVIDENCE
1 to 3.2	Barely worth mentioning
3.2 to 10	Substantial
> 10	Strong

in the table. Values smaller than 1 support model 1 and can be interpreted by using the relationship $B_{01} = B_{10}^{-1}$.

Generally speaking, the marginal likelihoods are hard to compute. However, we will see that in object tracking, the measurement model is exactly what is needed to calculate the likelihood. This is because the measurement model is exactly defined to provide $g(Z|X)$, that is the likelihood of the measurements Z conditioned on the state X .

III. PARAMETER MONITORING METHODS

In the following sections, we will give details about the two different monitoring methods. The first is based on parameter estimation, and the second is based on model comparison.

We assume in both methods a state-independent detection probability p_d and constant clutter intensity $\kappa = \lambda/A$. This is mainly to focus on the relevant ideas and to be able to provide closed formulas. It is possible to formulate the methods more generally.

A. Method based on Parameter Estimation

The first method is essentially a two-step method:

- 1) Estimate the parameter of interest.
- 2) Use the HDI of the estimate and the ROPE of the parameter to decide whether the parameter is ok or not.

For the first step, we use the method described in Section II-C for the clutter rate and the one of Section II-D for the detection probability.

For the second step, we have two degrees of freedom. First, we have to choose the ROPE of the parameter. To make this decision, practical experience with the filter at hand is needed. The decision should reflect the sensitivity of the filter with regard to that parameter.

Here, we choose the ROPE based on Monte-Carlo (MC) simulations for an LMB filter with an update based on Gibbs sampling [12]. We use the setup described in Section IV-A to perform 20 MC experiments for every combination of scenario and filter parameter. Note that all other parameters of the filter match the simulation parameters. We use the generalized optimal sub-pattern assignment (GOSPA) metric [13] to compare the different tracking results.

Figure 3 shows the result for the clutter rate parameter. The actual clutter rate used to simulate the scenario is shown on the y-axis, and the clutter rate used by the filter is shown on the x-axis. Accordingly, the filter only performs worse than optimal for a scenario with a given clutter rate when the filter parameter is below that value, i.e., left of the diagonal in Fig. 3. This means we can define a large, practically one-sided, ROPE with

$$\text{ROPE}(\lambda) = [0, \lambda]. \quad (12)$$

Fig. 3: Determining the ROPE for the clutter rate of an LMB filter. Note that the scenario is generated with the clutter rate on the y-axis while the filter uses the clutter rate on the x-axis. The performance is measured with the mean GOSPA metric. The black circles indicate the evaluation points; between these values, the GOSPA value is interpolated.

Fig. 4: Determining the ROPE for the detection probability of an LMB filter. Note that the scenario is generated with the detection probability on the y-axis while the filter uses the parameter on the x-axis. The performance is measured with the mean GOSPA metric.

With this definition, it is not a problem if the current estimate and its HDI are below the parameter used.

Figure 4 shows the same result for the detection probability. Based on this result, we propose an ROPE with

$$\text{ROPE}(p_d) = [p_d - 0.05, p_d + 0.05]. \quad (13)$$

Note that these results only apply to the aforementioned filter and are not straightforward to transfer to other filters or implementations. However, the described setup can be used to derive the ROPE for other filters and their parameters.

The second degree of freedom is the HDI. For our evaluations, we choose the commonly used 89% HDI.

B. Method based on Model Comparison

As mentioned in Section II-F, the Bayes factor can be used to distinguish between competing models after observing

some data. Here, a model means one specific tracking algorithm with one specific parameterization. As data, we have the measurements.

This means that, ultimately, we would like to decide between model 0, with parameters $\mathcal{P} = p$, and model 1, with parameters $\mathcal{P} \neq p$. In this context, it is more natural and useful to express the second case differently: as a model where the parameters are from a broader interval $\mathcal{P} \in I$ that might also include p . Here, M_0 is the reference model or reference parameter configuration used by the tracking algorithm. M_1 is the alternative, where we assume that the parameters follow some distribution, i.e., are in some broader range. This means, $B_{01} > 1$ supports the chosen filter parameters and $B_{01} < 1$ indicate wrong filter parameters. To calculate B_{01} , we look at $\pi(Z|M_0)$ and $\pi(Z|M_1)$ individually.

In the following, we use the special form of the GLMB update equations to demonstrate the approach. However, similar computations may also be possible for other tracking algorithms because their update equations often have a similar structure, e.g., for MBM-based filters.

Computing $\pi(Z|M_0)$ is straightforward. This value is the normalization factor of the update Eq. (2), which is often computed implicitly or explicitly during the filter update step anyway. For the GLMB Update, it is given by [6],

$$\pi(Z|M_0) = \sum_{\substack{(I,\xi) \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{L}) \times \Xi \\ \theta \in \Theta}} w^{I,\xi} \mathcal{L}(I, \xi, \theta), \quad (14)$$

$$\mathcal{L}(I, \xi, \theta) = \frac{e^{-\lambda} \lambda^{|Z_C|}}{A^{|Z_C|} |Z_C|!} p_d^{|D|} \mathcal{M}^D (1 - p_d)^{|M|}, \quad (15)$$

where Z_C are the clutter measurements, D is the set of all detected tracks, M is the set of all missed tracks, and $\mathcal{M}(l) = \langle p^\xi(\cdot, l), g(z_{\theta(l)} | \cdot, l) \rangle$ is the measurement likelihood. Note that all three sets are completely specified through a hypothesis (I, ξ, θ) , in detail

$$D = \{l \in I : \theta(l) \neq 0\}, \quad (16)$$

$$M = \{l \in I : \theta(l) = 0\}, \quad (17)$$

$$Z_C = Z \setminus \{\theta(l) : l \in D\}. \quad (18)$$

To compute $\pi(Z|M_1)$, we use the fact that $[M_1|\mathcal{P} = p] = M_0$. This means

$$\pi(Z|M_1) = \int \pi(Z|M_0, \mathcal{P}) d\mathcal{P}. \quad (19)$$

Then, using Eq. (15), it follows:

$$\pi(Z|M_1) = \sum_{\substack{(I,\xi) \in \mathcal{F}(\mathbb{L}) \times \Xi \\ \theta \in \Theta}} w^{I,\xi} \int \mathcal{L}(I, \xi, \theta) d\mathcal{P} \quad (20)$$

Now, it depends on the parameters one wants to investigate. We continue with, first, $\mathcal{P} = \lambda$ and, second, $\mathcal{P} = p_d$. One can also treat the two parameters together. However, we found that the clutter parameter often had more influence on the likelihood, e.g., when the number of clutter is higher than the number of objects. Therefore, errors in one of them may not be visible when looking at them combined. Additionally, looking at them separately may provide more information.

So, when $\mathcal{P} = \lambda$, it follows

$$\int \mathcal{L}(I, \xi, \theta) d\lambda = p_d^{|D|} \mathcal{M}^D (1 - p_d)^{|M|} \frac{\int e^{-\lambda} \lambda^{|Z_C|} d\lambda}{A^{|Z_C|} |Z_C|!} \quad (21)$$

The integral now depends on the distribution with which we want to compare the reference model. We use $\lambda \sim \text{Gamma}(\alpha, \beta)$. Then, the integral is given by

$$\int e^{-\lambda} \lambda^{|Z_C|} d\lambda = \frac{\beta^\alpha}{(\beta + 1)^{|Z_C| + \alpha}} \frac{\Gamma(|Z_C| + \alpha)}{\Gamma(\alpha)}. \quad (22)$$

Note that you can also choose other distributions, e.g., a uniform distribution over some interval. The only requirement is that the resulting integral is well-defined.

When looking at the detection probability, i.e., $\mathcal{P} = p_d$, it follows

$$\int \mathcal{L}(I, \xi, \theta) dp_d = \frac{e^{-\lambda} \lambda^{|Z_C|}}{A^{|Z_C|} |Z_C|!} \mathcal{M}^D \int p_d^{|D|} (1 - p_d)^{|M|} dp_d. \quad (23)$$

Again, we can choose the distribution of p_d . We use $p_d \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha_0, \alpha_1)$. Then,

$$\int p_d^{|D|} (1 - p_d)^{|M|} dp_d = \frac{B(\alpha_0 + |D|, \alpha_1 + |M|)}{B(\alpha_0, \alpha_1)}. \quad (24)$$

Note that for the implementation, the associations are only computed once (based on the reference model), and only the weights are re-calculated for the alternative model. This reduces the computational effort but may lower the accuracy because, in this case, only hypotheses where the reference model has relevant weights are computed. Hypotheses with significant weight in the alternative model but with small weight in the reference model may therefore be excluded, which may influence the outcome towards the reference model.

Also, note that the above-described method can be used to define a new filter whose parameters follow a certain distribution. This allows, e.g., to directly use the result of the previously described estimation methods in the filter. However, this is outside of the scope of this paper.

As a final note, we want to mention that grouping, i.e., splitting the distribution into multiple independent parts, can also be handled properly.

IV. SIMULATION EXPERIMENTS

In this section, we test our methods on different simulation setups.

A. Monte Carlo Simulation Setup

For our MC simulations, we first create random ground-truth tracks. Within a 100 m \times 100 m simulation area uniformly distributed between 20 and 50 objects appear at the first time step and disappear at the end of the simulation. Each track moves according to a nearly constant velocity model with standard derivation $a_x = a_y = 0.1 \text{ m/s}^2$. Every track generates a measurement with detection probability p_d . The detection probability is uniformly distributed between 0.5 and 0.99 but constant over one simulation. Each measurement contains the track's x and y position, with a variance of 3 m^2 .

Fig. 5: Exemplary ground-truth paths used for the MC simulations. Note that also the clutter rate and detection probability of a scenario are chosen randomly.

Additional clutter measurements are uniformly distributed over the simulation area. The number of clutter is Poisson distributed with rate λ . The clutter rate is uniformly distributed between 1 and 50 but constant over one simulation. If not indicated otherwise, the filter uses parameters that match the scenario setup, and a single sensor is used. Figure 5 shows an example of the so-generated ground-truth paths. If not stated otherwise, 50 MC runs for every experiment are done.

B. Monitoring the Clutter Rate

Figure 6 shows the result for the clutter rate monitoring with the Bayes factor. It uses the Gamma distribution with a mean of 20 and a variance of 300 as the alternative model. A Bayes factor > 1 supports the filter parameter used, and a factor < 1 supports the alternative model. Note that in Fig. 6, the average of the logarithm of the Bayes factor is shown. The figure shows that the method works in general. Scenarios where the filter parameter matches the real parameter, i.e., on the diagonal, have a Bayes factor > 1 , and non-matching parameters have a Bayes factor < 1 . Unfortunately, the range of the Bayes factor is not ideal. Mismatching scenarios have a very low Bayes factor, whereas the highest Bayes factor is only around 7. Other values fall in the range of $1/3.2$ to 3.2 , which, according to Table I, does not allow for drawing conclusions. This could be solved by combining multiple time steps. However this is not further investigated in this paper.

Figure 7 shows the results for monitoring the clutter rate with the ROPE and HDI. The figure shows the estimated clutter rate encoded by color. As before, the small circles indicate the actual evaluated parameter configurations. If a specific configuration is considered ok, i.e. the ROPE and HDI overlap, a green circle is drawn; otherwise, a red circle. Note that for this, the HDI is averaged over the whole duration of the simulation. The results show that the clutter rate estimation works in most cases well. Problems arise when the filter clutter rate is way too low. Then, the estimate underestimates the true value. This is caused by the dependency of the estimation with the filter parameter, see Section II-C and [3]. Because of the chosen ROPE, only configurations where the filter clutter rate is too low are marked as not ok, i.e., by a red dot. By

Fig. 6: The Bayes factor for the clutter rate parameter. The actual parameter used to generate the scenario is on the y-axis, and the parameter used by the filter is on the x-axis. The figure shows the mean log Bayes factor.

Fig. 7: The estimated clutter rate. The actual parameter used to generate the scenario is on the y-axis, and the parameter used by the filter is on the x-axis. The colors encode the estimated clutter rate. A green circle indicates that this value is considered ok, and a red circle indicates that it is not ok.

changing the ROPE, also a too high clutter rate could be detected.

C. Monitoring the Detection Probability

Figure 8 shows the result for the detection probability monitoring with the Bayes factor. It uses the prior distribution of Fig. 2, i.e., the Beta distribution with $\alpha_0 = 6$ and $\alpha_1 = 2$ as the alternative model. As before, the range of the Bayes factor is not ideal. The lowest value is approximately $1/20$, and the highest value is approximately 2. According to Table I, this means the filter parameter can never be confirmed, only a mismatch can be detected. Combining multiple time steps could solve this issue.

Figure 9 shows the results for monitoring the detection probability with the ROPE and HDI. As with the clutter rate, the estimation works well if the filter parameter is close to the true value. However, if the two values differ, the estimation method is negatively affected. This results in falsely accepting

Fig. 8: The Bayes factor for the detection probability parameter. The actual parameter used to generate the scenario is on the y-axis, and the parameter used by the filter is on the x-axis. The figure shows the mean Bayes factor.

Fig. 9: The estimated detection probability. The actual parameter used to generate the scenario is on the y-axis, and the parameter used by the filter is on the x-axis. The colors encode the estimated detection probability. A green circle indicates that this value is considered ok, and a red circle indicates that it is not ok.

wrong filter parameters. For example, in the scenario with detection probability 0.6, filter parameters from 0.5 up to 0.8 are considered ok. The reason for this is the dependency of the estimation with the filter, see Section II-D and [4].

D. Monitoring both Parameters in a Dynamic Scenario

In this experiment, we have two sensors with dynamically changing parameters. The multi-sensor filter is implemented with an iterator corrector scheme, i.e., the posterior after the update of the first sensor is used as prior to the update of the second sensor. Figure 10 shows the scenario parameters for the two sensors. The filter uses the parameters of time step 0 for the whole simulation.

The effect of this parameter mismatch on the filter results is shown by the GOSPA in Fig. 11. In the figure, the GOSPA is divided into localization, missed, and false, measuring the spatial error, the number of missed objects, and the number

Fig. 10: The time-varying detection probability and clutter rate of the dynamic scenario. The parameters of sensor 0 are shown by the solid lines, and the parameters of sensor 1 are shown by the dashed lines.

Fig. 11: The GOSPA for the dynamic scenario. Note, that individual GOSPA components do not simply sum up to the overall value.

Fig. 12: The Bayes factor for the clutter rate for the dynamic scenario.

Fig. 13: The Bayes factor for the detection probability for the dynamic scenario.

Fig. 14: The HDI and ROPE for the detection probability for the dynamic scenario. The estimated detection probability is shown by the solid lines. The shaded areas show the HDI of the estimation and the dashed lines indicate the lower and upper bound of the ROPE.

Fig. 15: The HDI and ROPE for the clutter rate for the dynamic scenario. The estimated clutter rate is shown by the solid lines. The shaded areas show the HDI of the estimation, and the dashed lines indicate the lower and upper bounds of the ROPE.

of false tracks, respectively. The results show that a wrong detection probability mainly affects the missed tracks, and a wrong clutter rate mainly affects the false tracks.

Figure 12 and Fig. 13 show the Bayes factor for the clutter rate and the detection probability. The areas with the parameter mismatch are clearly visible with a Bayes factor well below 1. However, the same issue exists as with the previous results: the Bayes factor of matching areas is only in the range of 1.5 to 3. Also, in this case, multiple time steps should be combined to increase the range of the Bayes factor.

Figure 14 and Fig. 15 show the results for the HDI and ROPE approach. The estimated detection probability of the two sensors is shown by the solid lines. The shaded areas show the HDI of the estimation, and the dashed lines indicate the ROPE of the parameter used by the filter. Areas where the two intervals do not overlap, indicate a parameter mismatch.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this work, we proposed two different methods for monitoring two different parameters of the multi-object measurement model. The first method is based on an estimate of the parameters and compares the estimate with the parameter used by the filter. The advantage of this method is that it not only provides monitoring but, naturally, also an estimate of the parameter. This allows an adaptation of

the filter if there is a mismatch. The disadvantage is that specifying the ROPE is highly filter-specific.

The second method is based on the Bayes factor. It compares the multi-object measurement likelihood of the filter with that of an alternative measurement model. This method's advantage is that it can provide support and, therefore, validate the parameters used by the filter. However, in case of a mismatch, no further information about the actual parameter can be deduced.

As further work, we want to investigate an adaptation based on the estimation and schemes to combine multiple time steps to increase the expressiveness of the method with the Bayes factor.

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